

High-Resolution Multi-Physics Modeling of the PULSTAR Core

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ABSTRACT

The verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification (VVUQ) of high-fidelity, high-resolution multi-physics models is challenging due to the scarcity of experimental data at the pin level and to the significant computational cost involved. The PULSTAR reactor at North Carolina State University holds strong potential for supporting such VVUQ activities. In this work, two different high-resolution multi-physics models are developed and compared on the initial core configuration of PULSTAR. The first model employs a Serpent-CTF coupling developed at NCSU, while the second uses an APOLLO3-THEDI coupling developed at the French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission. The results demonstrate satisfactory agreement between the two models, with a difference of 5% for the pin-power peaking, and below 350 pcm for the k_{eff} . The average discrepancy for the fuel temperature is under 3.5 K, while for the coolant temperature rise is below 0.3 K. The discrepancies between the two models are more pronounced near the top and bottom reflectors. Additional studies with THEDI reinforced the choice of using tabulated fuel properties based on CTFFuel calculations and provided a first estimate of the fuel and coolant properties for the current PULSTAR core. Future work will focus on further improving the multi-physics models and performing uncertainty propagation.

Keywords: multi-physics, high-resolution, PULSTAR, Serpent, APOLLO3

1. INTRODUCTION

High-fidelity multi-physics Modeling and Simulation (M&S) is important to support the design of light-water reactors (LWRs), advanced reactors, and small modular reactors, as well as the development of new fuel technologies. Core design, operation optimization and safety analysis are examples of applications that rely on accurate high-fidelity, high-resolution multi-physics calculations. The outcomes of all these applications depend on the reliability of the model predictions, which is established through Verification, Validation, and Uncertainty Quantification (VVUQ). VVUQ of scientific M&S is a set of processes and methods developed throughout the past 70 years across various engineering disciplines [1]. Verification assesses whether the mathematical model is implemented correctly in the computational tool. Validation evaluates the degree to which the computational models reproduce relevant measured data. Uncertainty quantification is the process of identifying, characterizing and propagating all sources of uncertainties into the model predictions. In applications where experimental data are limited, code-to-code comparisons provide intermediate steps to establish model consistency, although they cannot be a substitute for validation.

Reactor multi-physics simulation tools are in general classified into two categories:

- Traditional multi-physics M&S approaches that are assembly-resolved. They use strong modeling approximations in the coupled physics (e.g. two-group diffusion approximation, no coolant cross-flows).

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- Novel multi-physics tools that relax several modeling approximations (e.g., transport equation, radial coolant cross-flows) and further refine the prediction resolution to the pin or even sub-pin level.

Examples of novel multi-physics models can be found in [2] for advanced reactors using Griffin-BISON MOOSE-based codes, and in [3] for LWRs using nTRACER-CTF codes. Additionally, several multi-physics coupling frameworks between Monte Carlo neutronics codes and subchannel thermal-hydraulics codes have been developed, such as Serpent-SUBCHANFLOW-TRANSURANUS in [4]. One of the main challenges in the VVUQ of these high-fidelity, high-resolution models is the scarcity of relevant experimental data [5], [6]. This statement is even more valid at a pin level resolution.

Considering the scarcity of high-resolution experimental datasets, university research reactors offer opportunities for controlled validation of high-fidelity M&S frameworks. The PULSTAR reactor at North Carolina State University (NCSU) is the only university research reactor in the United States that operates with LWR-type fuel at high power, (i.e. UO_2 fuel rods in pin geometry with power level allowing feedback)¹. PULSTAR has the characteristics needed to provide an experimental platform suitable for the VVUQ of high-fidelity, high-resolution multi-physics models. Historical measurements of excess reactivity have been performed at regular intervals [7], and assembly-level power distribution data are available for model validation. Future pin-level measurements are envisioned, specifically targeting the validation and uncertainty quantification of the models developed at NCSU and at the Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission (CEA, France). In this work, preliminary code-to-code comparisons are performed for the modeling of the initial PULSTAR core with two different high-resolution multi-physics models: a Serpent-CTF model developed at NCSU and an APOLLO3-THEDI model developed at CEA.

2. PULSTAR CORE CONFIGURATION

The PULSTAR reactor is an open-pool, 1 MW_{th} light-water reactor. Its core consists of a 6×6 rectangular lattice, in which each position hosts either a fuel assembly or a reflector assembly. The fuel assemblies contain UO_2 fuel rods enriched to either 4 % or 6 % in ^{235}U , arranged in a 5×5 array with a pitch of 1.33 cm in the x direction and 1.54 cm in the y direction. Each fuel rod contains 40 fuel pellets, yielding an active fuel height of 60.96 cm. Water, graphite, and/or beryllium (Be) have been historically used as reflector materials. Since first criticality in 1972, 12 core configurations have been used. A typical core configuration comprises 25 fuel assemblies arranged in a 5×5 rectangular lattice with a pitch of 7.71 cm in the x -direction and 8.10 cm in the y -direction, surrounded by reflector assemblies occupying the remaining core positions.

The core is mounted on a grid plate positioned above a plenum chamber. Near the core boundary, a graphite thermal column is present, together with six beam tubes that may be either flooded or voided. PULSTAR's moderator-to-fuel volume ratio is low (≈ 1.14), compared to about 2.00 in typical PWRs [8]), so the removal of water from these beam tubes (voiding) has a strong neutronic worth. These components can therefore have a significant impact on the M&S of the core. Additional support and instrumentation structures surround the core, but their neutronic influence is comparatively minor and they are therefore not modeled in detail.

Reactivity control is provided by four silver-indium-cadmium control "rods" (plate-type absorbers with a composition of 80 %–15 %–5 %) inserted into two guide channels located between adjacent fuel assembly columns. The reactor is cooled by forced downward convection using a pump located at the bottom of the plenum chamber. The main PULSTAR operating conditions are summarized in Table I.

To accurately model the current PULSTAR configuration, the irradiation history of each fuel assembly must be reconstructed across all past core layouts. As shown in [7], stand-alone Monte Carlo simu-

lations are sufficient for this task. In a separate study, Serpent was used to deplete all pins for every historical configuration.

In this work, the first PULSTAR core from 1972 (Core 0) is modeled using two multi-physics coupling frameworks, that are discussed in the next section, under hot full-power (HFP), all-rods-out (ARO) conditions. This configuration, shown in Figure 1a, features all beam tubes in the flooded state; five of them, together with the thermal column, are visible in the figure. Modeling Core 0 provides a baseline for future analyses of the current Core 12 (Figure 1b), where upcoming experiments will be performed.

Table I. PULSTAR nominal operating conditions.

Parameter	Units	Value
Thermal Power	MW_{th}	1
Inlet coolant temperature	K	313.75
Outlet coolant temperature	K	321.65
Average fuel temperature	K	418.15
Mass flow rate	kg/s	31.55

Figure 1. PULSTAR radial geometries for Cores 0 and 12 generated with Serpent. Yellow fuel rods are enriched to 4 %, and red fuel rods to 6 %. The thermal column is shown in brown, while the Be reflectors in dark green. The beam tubes are either flooded (cyan) or voided (white).

3. MULTI-PHYSICS MODELS

An "NCSU" and a "CEA" core model were developed, using JEFF-3.1.1 nuclear data library. The NCSU model couples Serpent (v2.2.1) with CTF (v4.3). The CEA model uses APOLLO3 and THEDI.

- Serpent is a continuous-energy Monte Carlo reactor physics code developed by VTT that supports steady-state, depletion calculations [9].
- CTF (v4.3) is a three-dimensional subchannel thermal-hydraulics code based on a two-fluid, three-field formulation for two-phase flow. CTFFuel solves the 1D heat conduction equation for each fuel pin across axial nodes. A model for the burnup-dependent degradation of fuel thermal conductivity is available. CTF has been validated for various LWR applications [10]. It is developed and maintained by the Reactor Dynamics and Fuel Modeling Group (RDFMG) at NCSU.

- APOLLO3 (v3.1) is a deterministic neutronics platform offering a several transport and diffusion solvers for lattice and full-core calculations. APOLLO3 has been widely used in R&D efforts involving VVUQ, solver development, and multi-physics coupling, among others [11]. In this work, the MOC solver is used in the lattice step to generate Multi-Parameter Output (MPO) cross sections for fuel rods, reflectors, and structural regions. For core-level calculations, the MINARET discrete-ordinates solver is used.
- THEDI is a thermal-hydraulic solver with two-phase, multi-1D axial flow capabilities. The 1D heat conduction equation is solved in each fuel rod. THEDI is coupled to APOLLO3 as an external library [12].

In the NCSU model, the Serpent calculations are set with 2×10^5 neutrons per cycle, 1000 active and 200 inactive cycles, yielding a k_{eff} uncertainty of about 7 pcm. The fission source entropy and peak power were tracked to ensure convergence. A 625×40 pin-power mesh was used, with ten axial nodes and a radial model extent of 100 cm and 150 cm of axial water above the core. Cross-flows are considered within each fuel assembly but not between assemblies. This approximation is considered reasonable based on the fuel-assembly box design. In the Serpent–CTF coupling, CTF provides Serpent with the average fuel temperature (T_F), coolant temperature (T_M), and coolant density (ρ_M), and Serpent returns the pin-power distribution to CTF. For the cladding temperature (T_C) in node i , it is assumed $T_{C,i} = T_{M,i}$. For coolant channels not in direct contact with fuel (e.g., guide channels), and for regions outside the active core, the inlet coolant conditions are applied. The Serpent–CTF coupling used a 1.0 % convergence threshold for T_F , T_M , ρ_M and power, evaluated using the L_2 norm. Further optimization of the coupling technique is needed in the future to improve the convergence behavior in the presence of statistical uncertainty. In practice, the coupling is relatively weak and converges within only a few iterations, and one-way coupling results already show close agreement with the two-way coupling.

In the CEA model for the APOLLO3–THEDI, the lattice calculations used the MOC solver, while the core calculations employed the MINARET solver with an S_4 quadrature and the same ten axial nodes. There are radially one node per fuel assembly, since THEDI does not account for cross-flows. Although coolant properties are computed at the assembly level, $T_{F,i}$ are evaluated for each individual fuel rod using the pin-power distribution obtained from APOLLO3. The thermal conductivity and pellet-cladding gap conductance fuel properties are provided through tables generated with CTFFuel to avoid discrepancies and ensure consistency between the THEDI and CTFFuel models. In addition, CTFFuel incorporates fuel behavior models that are not available in THEDI, including (1) the degradation of the thermal conductivity with burnup and (2) a dynamic gap conductance predicted based on local temperature and burnup. These fuel properties are tabulated as a function of the average $T_{F,i}$ and burnup. Convergence criteria of 0.1 % for temperatures and power, and 0.1 pcm for k_{eff} , were applied. Similar to the Serpent–CTF, the coupling is not very strong, leading to a convergence after few outer iterations.

4. RESULTS

Four sets of results are presented: (1) Serpent–CTF, (2) APOLLO3–THEDI, (3) a standalone analysis that examines the sensitivity of THEDI predictions to the fuel-property tables generated with CTFFuel, and (4) a one-way Serpent–THEDI coupling for the current PULSTAR Core 12, including fuel depletion, to obtain an initial estimate of fuel and coolant conditions.

Among the available outputs, the discussion focuses on the axial relative power distribution (radially averaged), the radial power distribution (axially averaged), the T_F profile (pin radially and axially averaged), and the coolant temperature rise ΔT_M at the outlet.

4.1. Serpent-CTF Model - Core 0

The results of the Serpent-CTF are summarized in Table II. The results for the radial relative power distribution, radial average T_F , the ΔT_M , and the axial relative power distribution are shown in Figure 2.

The peak pin-power (Figure 2a) and T_F (Figure 2c) are located in the regions surrounding one of the control rod guides due to the enhanced neutron moderation. The average ΔT_M is consistent with the expected operational conditions listed in Table I.

Figure 2. Multi-physics results for the Serpent-CTF coupling

4.2. APOLLO3-THEDI Model - Core 0

The results of the APOLLO3-THEDI are summarized in Table II. The results for the radial relative power distribution, radial average T_F , ΔT_M , and the axial relative power distribution are presented in Figure 3. Overall, the comparison with the Serpent-CTF results shows a satisfactory agreement. Discrepancies below 5% for the peak power, under 3.5 K for the average T_F , and less than 350 pcm for the k_{eff} are obtained. The regions close to the top and bottom reflectors show larger discrepancies that are attributed to the control rods impact on the axial profile. This suggests the need for further refinement of the lattice calculations that include the control rods positioned on top of the core.

4.3. THEDI stand-alone Studies

The third set of results (Case 3) investigates how fuel-property models affect the predicted T_F in the Core 0 configuration. In the APOLLO3-THEDI results of Section 4.2, THEDI uses fuel thermal conductivity and pellet-cladding gap conductance taken from CTFFuel tables, tabulated as functions of the T_F and burnup. To assess the importance of these tables, two additional calculations are performed using fixed properties.

In Case 3a, the gap conductance is set to $3000 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, a common assumption when the gap is con-

Figure 3. Multi-physics results for the APOLLO3-THEDI coupling

 Table II. Core 0 results from the Serpent-CTF and APOLLO3-THEDI models. Code-to-code discrepancies (Δ) for integral quantities and local quantities at the pin and assembly (asb) levels are provided. \bar{T}_F and $\Delta\bar{T}_M$ indicate core averages.

Quantity	Serpent-CTF	APOLLO3-THEDI	Δ
k_{eff}	1.0130	1.0163	-330 pcm
F_Q^{max}	2.29	2.18	+0.11
$T_F^{\text{min}}/\bar{T}_F/T_F^{\text{max}}$ (pin)	340.8/396.1/485.7 K	343.4/397.1/486.3 K	-2.60/-1.00/-0.60 K
$\Delta T_M^{\text{min}}/\Delta\bar{T}_M/\Delta T_M^{\text{max}}$ (asb)	5.08/7.46/9.91 K	5.23/7.43 /9.75 K	-0.15/+0.03/+0.16 K

sidered fully open. Figure 4a shows that the resulting radial T_F differs by up to 30 K relative to the CTFFuel-based prediction. In Case 3b, the fuel thermal conductivity is fixed at 6 W/mK. The impact is smaller but still noticeable, with differences up to 6 K (Figure 4b). Given that the average T_F across the core between hot zero-power (HZP) and HFP conditions is at the order of 100 K, these deviations are significant, indicating that THEDI benefits from CTFFuel-derived property tables to maintain consistency and limit model discrepancies.

The fourth set of results uses Serpent pin power predictions for the current Core 12 at HFP ARO conditions in a one way coupling with THEDI. This study was performed as part of the work to develop the THEDI model for Core 12 that accounts for irradiation effects. The fuel irradiation across all core configurations has been considered. Core 12 contains 6 fuel assemblies enriched to 6% in ^{235}U . The results

for the radial T_F , and ΔT_M are provided in Figure 5. From Figure 5a the 6% enriched fuel assemblies are clearly distinguishable, exhibiting higher T_F . Although the T_F distribution changes notably, the core average remains comparable to that of Core 0. Similar behavior is observed for the ΔT_M (Figure 5b).

Figure 4. Impact of THEDI fuel properties modeling on the radial average fuel temperature.

Figure 5. One-way preliminary coupled results for Core 12.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The PULSTAR reactor at NCSU holds strong potential for supporting the VVUQ of high-fidelity, high-resolution multi-physics M&S, which is one of the key challenges in nuclear engineering. In this work, two high-fidelity multi-physics models were developed and compared for the initial PULSTAR Core 0 configuration: Serpent-CTF and APOLLO3-THEDI.

The code-to-code comparisons show good agreement, with a pin-power peaking difference of about 5% and a k_{eff} difference below 350 pcm. Average discrepancies remain below 3.5 K for the fuel temperature and under 0.3 K for the coolant temperature rise. Larger deviations are observed near the axial reflectors, indicating the need for improved modeling in the APOLLO3 lattice calculations. Complementary THEDI studies show the importance of consistent fuel-property modeling. Fixing the pellet-cladding gap conductance at a constant value (rather than using CTFFuel-based tables) alters the predicted fuel temperature by up to 36 K, while fixing the thermal conductivity leads to changes of up to 6 K. Given that the core-average fuel temperature increase from HZP to HFP is at the order of 100 K, these effects are significant.

Future work will focus on refining APOLLO3-THEDI axial resolution, improving the multi-physics coupling strategies, and performing full uncertainty propagation as part of the broader VVUQ effort.

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